

Towards a Maturity Assessment Framework for MBSE Adoption: Challenges, Pitfalls and Best Practices

Tobias Henoeckl, Charlotte Verbruggen^{ORCID}, and Dominik Bork^{ORCID}

Business Informatics Group, TU Wien, Austria
{charlotte.verbruggen,dominik.bork}@tuwien.ac.at

This document is supplementary material for the paper "**Towards a Maturity Assessment Framework for MBSE Adoption: Results from a Meta-Synthesis**" and consists of two parts. Part 1 presents the self-assessment questionnaire that can be used to determine the maturity level of an organization in their MBSE adoption. Part 2 gives a detailed description for each Challenge (C), Pitfall (P) and Best Practice (BP) from the maturity assessment framework. The Challenges, Pitfalls and Best Practices are organized first into maturity levels, and then into categories.

1 Part 1: Self-Assessment Questionnaire

Instructions: If you can answer all questions of Level 1 with "Yes", then you may continue with the questions of level 2 and so forth. If you encounter a question of a specific level that you answer with "No", then your current MBSE adoption effort belongs to this level.

1.1 Level 1: Initial Preparation

1. Is there a shared understanding of MBSE across all involved teams and disciplines? (What MBSE encompasses, what models are used for, what they enable, etc.)
2. Is the workforce familiar with SE or the systems thinking approach? Do they understand thinking holistically about the system - understanding interactions and interdependencies between subsystems?
3. Have you already taken steps to clearly communicate the value of MBSE to relevant stakeholders?
4. Have you considered potential resistance from (senior) employees and provided training or developed plans to address skepticism and reluctance to change?

1.2 Level 2: Planning & Structure

1. Has leadership committed to supporting MBSE, providing resources and backing its adoption and integration also for the long-term?

2. Have you defined both short-term and long-term goals for the MBSE adoption, together with a clear scope for what the organization aims to achieve?
3. Is there a core MBSE team in place with a clear role assignment, tailored training and a plan for knowledge transfer across departments?
4. Does your organization have the required IT infrastructure to support the collaborative MBSE work, including proper tools, licenses, processing power and storage?
5. Have you set up clear measures to track both the progress of the adoption and ROI from the MBSE effort?

1.3 Level 3: Pilot Projects

1. Have you considered off-cycle and on-cycle pilot project trade-offs and chosen a suitable project to start with?
2. Do you clearly define the purpose and scope of each model, defining specific engineering questions the model is meant to answer?
3. Are your pilot MBSE modeling efforts supported by a well-structured model architecture that plans for both system and subsystem levels and is able to evolve with the project?
4. Have you established standardized modeling practices, limiting the use of complex features in the modeling language to ensure consistency across teams?
5. Are you conducting regular model validation and verification processes, such as stakeholder reviews and automated checks, to ensure models are accurate and usable?

1.4 Level 4: Scaling MBSE Adoption

1. Have you established reusable model libraries and modular structures and do you enforce their use across projects?
2. Are your models designed with flexibility in mind, allowing them to grow and evolve?
3. Are models regularly maintained and updated with new data to ensure they remain relevant and accurate throughout the product lifecycle?
4. Are models the main artifact in your development life cycle?
5. Are your models relevant to multiple stakeholders?

2 Part 2: Challenges, Pitfalls and Best Practices

This section gives a detailed description for each Challenge (C), Pitfall (P) and Best Practice (BP) from the maturity assessment framework. The Challenges, Pitfalls and Best Practices are organized first into maturity levels, and then into categories.

2.1 Level 1: Initial Preparation

Work Culture

– C1: Cultural Change Resistance

Implementing MBSE often encounters significant cultural resistance within organizations. Engineers and stakeholders are traditionally accustomed to working with and reviewing documents, making the transition to models as primary artifacts a substantial shift in established workflows. Phrases like *"This is how we have always done it"* embody the inherent resistance to adopting new methodologies. This resistance is further compounded when key players lack adequate training and time to adapt, leading to a deficiency in understanding MBSE's value and processes. Such gaps not only foster skepticism but can also create a belief among employees that their systems are too large or complex to be effectively integrated into an MBSE framework. Without addressing these cultural and educational barriers, the transition to MBSE can face obstacles that hinder its successful adoption and integration. Recognizing and proactively managing this cultural resistance is paramount, as it stands among the greatest challenges organizations must overcome in their MBSE journey [6][14][8][19][20][7][42][41][1].

Knowledge and Skills

– C2: Lack of Perceived Value and High Upfront Investment Cost

One of the primary challenges in adopting MBSE is the lack of perceived value among stakeholders, particularly in the early stages of implementation. The significant upfront investment required for MBSE, encompassing the establishment of models, tools, and trained personnel, can make it difficult to justify pilot projects or broader adoption initiatives. Stakeholders, especially those accustomed to traditional systems engineering methods, may be skeptical of the new approach, questioning whether it can deliver the same results as their familiar processes. This skepticism is often fueled by concerns over the unknowns associated with MBSE, such as its ability to produce the expected products and insights more efficiently or with higher quality. Generic claims of improved efficiency and effectiveness are typically insufficient to convince these stakeholders [19][28][29][34][15][2][7][35][26][42][41][1].

– C3: Lack of Skilled Workforce and Impact on Workforce Dynamics

Another challenge in the transition to MBSE is the general lack of skilled MBSE engineers within many organizations. Most companies do not have a readily available workforce that is equipped to easily transition to MBSE, as it requires a specialized set of skills and knowledge that many current employees may not possess [6][19][34][15][25][20][1].

This skill gap can lead organizations to seek new talent, which can inadvertently threaten the job security and satisfaction of established workers who feel their expertise in traditional processes is becoming obsolete. Senior engineers, who are typically the technical experts in the current processes,

may feel that the new tools and methodologies associated with MBSE undermine their existing knowledge base. This perceived threat can result in uncertainty and decreased job satisfaction, as the senior engineers struggle to see their place in the new MBSE workflow. Instead of demonstrating organizational commitment by leading the transition, these engineers might experience stress and show resistance due to the strain and uncertainty associated with the change. Additionally, varying levels of MBSE knowledge and experience across the workforce, often influenced by factors like age or individual adaptability, can lead to further resistance to change, compounding the difficulty of a smooth transition to MBSE [9][35].

– **C4: Divergent Understanding of MBSE.**

Another key challenge in adopting MBSE is the diverse and often conflicting mental images and understandings of what MBSE truly means. Design engineers across various disciplines need a foundational grasp of the MBSE approach to harness its benefits effectively. However, there is often confusion surrounding the many related terms and concepts, such as Model-Based Engineering (MBE), Model-Driven Engineering (MDE), or Model-Driven Development (MDD), which can lead to fragmented understanding. Additionally, when some people hear "diagrams" or "models", they might think of static MS Visio diagrams or other forms of static representations that offer no functionality beyond a snapshot of the system, compared to the dynamic and integrative capabilities actual MBSE models can offer. Some engineering domains may struggle with the specific tools and languages used in MBSE, such as mechanical engineers who may find SysML behavior diagrams challenging to interpret, as they are more accustomed to CAD tools. This disparity in understanding can be worsened by established discipline-specific thinking and the widespread use of specialized, often homegrown models that do not align with the holistic systems approach MBSE promotes. For MBSE to be successfully implemented, it is crucial to ensure that all stakeholders are on the same page regarding its concepts, evolution, and intended benefits, fostering a unified approach to systems thinking and engineering [6][15][20][35][41][36][1].

Management

– **BP1: Develop Holistic / Systems Thinking**

An important best practice that has to be approached in the early phase is the development of a holistic / systems thinking mindset in the workforce. MBSE is grounded in systems thinking, which requires professionals from diverse disciplines, like software, mechanical or electrical engineering, to see the bigger picture of system development. While not everyone needs to become an expert or has to be concerned with the intricate details of specific domains, all engineers should understand and engage with system models to ensure collaborative progress. Changing the mindset of how the people think about developing a system. This foundational understanding of systems engineering principles is essential, especially for those new to the discipline.

Without this shift in mindset and competency, the adoption of MBSE will struggle to succeed [14][3][34][15][27][11][1].

– **BP2: Develop Common Understanding**

A best practice in the initial stages of MBSE adoption is to ensure a basic awareness and common understanding of MBSE concepts across the organization. Again, not everybody needs to become an expert in modeling and the concepts involved, but it is essential that all employees, especially those involved in the definition and deployment phases, receive foundational training to align on MBSE principles and terminology. This helps avoid misunderstandings and fosters a unified approach. Further training should be tailored, with deeper knowledge reserved for those directly involved in model development, while others focus on understanding and interacting with models. Without this fundamental common understanding, the organization risks creating silos, where only a subset of engineers embrace MBSE, leading to division and undermining the overall effort. Evaluation and follow-up training can help address knowledge gaps that may arise over time [7][3][34][15][27][11][37][33].

– **BP3: Understand the Value of MBSE**

A best practice that is often mentioned, is making the advantages of the MBSE approach clear to everyone involved. It's essential that employees not only understand the theoretical benefits of MBSE, but also recognize how it can improve their own work, such as enhancing efficiency, quality, and reducing effort. This understanding helps build a unified workforce that supports the transition. Engineers are more likely to embrace the challenges of MBSE adoption if they can see its direct value in their daily activities. No amount of investment in tools and training will drive adoption unless the workforce perceives tangible benefits from using the MBSE approach. Targeted presentations and demonstrations of successful project experiences can further reinforce the value proposition and motivate engineers to collaborate towards successful adoption. This is crucial for fostering commitment and overcoming the inertia often encountered with organizational change [3][5][9][34][25][15][35][4][42].

2.2 Level 2: Planning and Structure

Knowledge and Skills

– **C5: Steep Learning Curve**

The adoption of MBSE is often hindered by a steep learning curve, especially for employees with little to no prior experience in modeling. Training is essential to ensure that users can effectively utilize MBSE tools and methodologies, but this training demands significant time and resources from both employees and management. In some cases, training has been rushed or even skipped, under the false assumption that MBSE methods are self-explanatory, leading to further complications down the line. Engineers without a background in modeling face particularly frustrating challenges, as they

must quickly grasp complex concepts and techniques. The costs associated with proper training, including both the financial investment and the time commitment, are necessary burdens that organizations must bear to build a basis for a successful transition towards MBSE. Without adequate training and support, the steep learning curve can impede progress and hinder the overall adoption of MBSE practices [19][32][15][25][2][26][37][42].

Management

– C6: Lack of Leadership Buy-In

A critical challenge in adopting MBSE is the lack of leadership buy-in and support. Strong leadership and management commitment are essential to overcome the institutional inertia that often emerges when substantial changes like MBSE happen. Without active engagement, support, and sponsorship from leadership, any MBSE initiative is unlikely to gain the momentum needed for success. Leaders are key decision-makers in planning the way forward. Their involvement is crucial for setting priorities, allocating resources, and fostering an organizational culture that embraces MBSE. Insufficient preparation, persuasion, and commitment from management can severely undermine the introduction and integration of MBSE methods and tools, leading to a faltering or failed implementation [19][28][29][34][40][25][8][20][41].

– C7: Measuring Progress and ROI

Another challenge in the adoption of MBSE is the difficulty in measuring progress and determining the return on investment (ROI). MBSE requires substantial upfront investment in tools, training, and processes, yet the benefits often take time to materialize, making it challenging to quantify immediate returns. To justify the investment and ensure continued support from stakeholders, it is crucial to establish clear metrics that track the progress of MBSE implementation within the organization. Additionally, a plan for measuring ROI should be developed, allowing for an assessment of how much value the company has gained from the transition over time. These measures are not only beneficial for evaluating the success of the adoption but also for making necessary adjustments to the strategy as needed, ensuring that the organization stays on track towards achieving its MBSE goals [15][25][8][42].

– C8: Defining a Clear Scope and Goals

A critical challenge in adopting MBSE is the need to establish a clear and well-defined scope and set of goals for the effort. This clarity helps management as well as employees further understand the purpose and future value that MBSE should bring to their work. Without a well-defined scope, there is a risk of over-enthusiasm, where organizations may attempt to implement too many aspects of MBSE at once, leading to overwhelm and potential failure in the transition. Clear, achievable goals help manage expectations and ensure that MBSE is seen as a tool to enhance SE, not replace it. Executive leadership plays a crucial role in this process, as they must make informed decisions that shape the path forward, balancing short-term, low-cost adoption

strategies with long-term, high-quality integration of MBSE. Additionally, managing user expectations is vital, as sales personnel of tools and trainings often make ambitious promises that can lead to unrealistic hopes. A common understanding of the "why" and "what" of MBSE adoption, supported by strong leadership, is essential to ensure a successful transition [14][8][25][8][20][42][1].

– **P1: Fast False Start**

A common pitfall in MBSE adoption is starting too quickly with too many initiatives at once, leading to overwhelm and potential failure. This "fast false start" can cause skepticism within the organization, reinforcing the belief that modeling doesn't work. To avoid this, it's important to introduce MBSE gradually, in smaller, manageable steps. This allows for a smoother transition, giving time to address any issues that arise and ensuring a more successful long-term adoption. Think big; start small [43][44].

– **P2: Underestimating the Learning Curve and Expert Involvement**

Another pitfall in MBSE adoption is underestimating the steep learning curve and over-relying on external experts. While experts can provide valuable guidance, the organization must take ownership of the process to ensure lasting success. Experts should assist during the transition but only be consulted selectively, allowing the organization to build internal expertise. Expecting immediate efficiency gains from MBSE, especially under project pressure, is unrealistic. Proper time and planning are essential to allow for learning and gradual improvement [43].

– **P3: Missing IT Infrastructure**

Failing to provide the necessary IT infrastructure to support the modeling environment can be a pitfall. Ensuring that the network, processing power, and storage capacity meet the demands of the modeling tools is essential. Without sufficient IT infrastructure, performance issues can arise, leading to delays, inefficiencies, and frustration among users, ultimately hindering the MBSE adoption process [32].

– **BP4: Focus on the purpose of the MBSE adoption**

A successful transition to MBSE depends on maintaining a clear focus on the purpose behind the change. Defining and communicating the goals, scope, and expected benefits of MBSE adoption from the outset is crucial. A clear end goal helps guide decisions throughout the process and prevents the effort from being sidetracked by new ideas that do not align with the original needs. While new concepts may arise during implementation, these should be carefully evaluated to ensure they do not divert attention from the core purpose. Organizations need to spend as much time understanding the problem space as they do developing solutions. By clearly articulating the purpose, the perceived complexity of MBSE can be minimized. The purpose should address key questions that the model is designed to answer and ensure that every stakeholder understands how MBSE aligns with business objectives. Communicating the "why" helps manage expectations and ensures that everyone involved remains focused on solving the right problems, preventing costly misdirection in the effort [14][7][3][28][29][5][34][25][15][27][4][11][33][41].

- **BP5: Leadership and Management Buy-In**

The success of MBSE adoption depends on strong leadership at multiple levels. The systems engineer tasked with leading the MBSE transition must play a leadership role, setting clear objectives, guiding the team, and managing the pace of change to ensure it is embraced by the workforce. Leadership is about understanding both people and processes, knowing when to push forward and when to hold back enthusiastic ideas until the organization is mature enough to continue with the next step. At the same time, buy-in from upper management is critical to provide the necessary resources, authority, and alignment of business goals with the MBSE transition. Management support is a key enabling factor, as it ensures a unified commitment across the organization, sustains momentum, and addresses concerns such as ROI and resource allocation, making MBSE adoption both possible and sustainable. Communication is key in this context, as convincing leadership can be challenging. It's essential to focus on *why* MBSE benefits the business rather than the *how* of its technical implementation [6][14][9][4][34][25][15][42][41].

- **BP6: "Think Big, Start Small, Evolve" [14]**

A strategic MBSE approach should begin by identifying clear, long-term goals, but manage the uncertainty and complexity of the transition by introducing small, manageable steps. Starting with a small, highly motivated group or a pilot project allows the organization to experiment in a controlled environment, learning from the specific challenges of the involved processes, domains, and tools. This approach helps to identify and resolve issues early, creating a foundation for broader adoption. Pilot projects serve as valuable trials where limited but targeted applications of MBSE can demonstrate tangible benefits. For instance, modeling just a few structural or behavioral elements needed for a specific capability can provide immediate value, which encourages expanding the modeling efforts incrementally. Each success builds confidence, skills, and management buy-in, helping the organization to progressively move from small-scale implementations toward an enterprise-wide MBSE approach. This incremental approach is key; crawl, walk, then run. Focus on achieving early, frequent successes to build momentum and confidence, ensuring steady progress and long-term sustainability [14][3][5][18][34][25][15][37][33][41][39].

- **BP7: Change Process Management**

Successfully transitioning to MBSE requires more than just technical expertise, it demands experienced guidance in managing the change process itself. Engaging professionals who have navigated similar transitions significantly increases the chances of success. These experts help continuously assess progress, identify training needs, and adapt strategies based on lessons learned. Effective change management includes fostering a culture of openness, evaluating and documenting business processes as well as providing ongoing coaching beyond initial training. This ensures that the organizational shift towards MBSE is well-supported, gradual, and adaptable to challenges [14][3][9][34][15][27][4][41].

- **BP8: Establish a MBSE Core Team**

Creating a dedicated MBSE team with clearly defined roles is frequently highlighted as a best practice for successful adoption. This core group should include designers with tailored training in the methodology and modeling language, model users trained to interpret system models, and tool owners proficient in MBSE tools who are responsible for adapting and evolving the tools to meet organizational needs. Additional key roles often mentioned in the literature include MBSE specialists, commonly referred to as MBSE Champions, who possess a strong modeling background and a deep understanding of their business unit's domain. These champions foster a network of experienced peers, guide and support the adoption process, and drive cultural change by attracting followers, securing resources, and ensuring corporate commitment. Champions often act as advisors to engineers starting their own projects, particularly when other support structures are limited. Another critical role is the model curator, tasked with optimizing the MBSE environment to enable accurate system analysis. In a single-source-of-truth solution, effective model curation is the foundation for reliable system decisions, as most, if not all, information derives from this source. Enterprises adopting MBSE that fail to address this personnel related practice, risk undermining their ability to execute their vision. Required skills and experience might not be readily available, but understanding and planning for changes in organizational structure, responsibilities and competencies is critical. By acquiring new specialists or providing the right level of training for each role, the complexity of MBSE can be significantly reduced for all stakeholders. With ongoing support and a clear division of responsibilities, the core MBSE team becomes a crucial driver of organizational alignment, ensuring that MBSE practices are effectively integrated and continuously improved across projects [7][5][13][34][17][25][15][26][4][37][42][33][41].

– **BP9: Knowledge Transfer and Collaborative Learning**

Facilitating knowledge transfer through mentoring, online forums, and peer social networks can be used to empower engineers to learn and adopt MBSE together. This collaborative approach helps bridge the gap between experienced engineers, who are less likely to be willing to embrace a change to established norms, and younger engineers more familiar and eager with digital tools [35]. Encouraging social interaction among learners fosters a supportive learning environment, increasing motivation and improving outcomes. By integrating both formal and informal knowledge sharing mechanisms, organizations can overcome resistance, enhance digital literacy, and sustain MBSE learning throughout the team [9][25][35][22].

– **BP10: Define Measures of Progress**

Establishing effective metrics to track the progress of MBSE adoption is particularly important given the delayed return on investment. Typical lower-level systems engineering metrics may not be as meaningful in an MBSE environment. For example, MBSE might reveal more requirement allocation errors, but this could be due to better error discovery rather than an increase in errors themselves [28]. Therefore, traditional measures might not fully capture the impact of MBSE. A dedicated MBSE business case should

be coupled with business criteria, focusing on progress indicators such as engagement with MBSE tools and quality improvements. Regularly tracking these tailored metrics allows for immediate feedback and adjustment of strategies, if necessary [7][28][29][34][25][15][24][16][4]. A specifically valuable resource in this context might be [16], who not only address the importance of measuring progress, but provide in-depth guidance on which measurements could be helpful to measure benefits and ultimately the success of the MBSE approach.

– **BP11: Accept the Learning Curve**

Organizations starting their MBSE transition have to accept and embrace the learning curve. When deciding on the pilot projects, it is important to choose initiatives that can accommodate the necessary learning efforts without jeopardizing critical timelines or business objectives. Otherwise employees might drop MBSE techniques in favor of established development methods due to the time pressure. Projects should be budgeted not only for delivering artifacts but also for covering the costs associated with this learning phase. Stakeholders additionally have to accept some initial redundancies as models are developed to capture data that is already contained in other sources (e.g. documents, presentations, etc.). The transition requires time and patience. Adequate training and supportive work relationships are vital to reducing uncertainty and resistance, thereby fostering job satisfaction and commitment to the change. Engineers need structured training on new digital engineering tools and modeling techniques to build confidence and expertise. By allocating dedicated time for learning and providing access to experts for guidance, organizations can mitigate stress and fatigue, preventing disengagement. Ultimately, accepting and supporting the learning curve helps create a positive environment where employees can adapt and thrive during the transition to MBSE, leading to a more successful and sustainable implementation [3][5][9][25][15].

– **BP12: General planning and Management Proposals.**

Organizations must approach the transition towards MBSE with the same rigor as any new technology, ensuring that the necessary knowledge and quality assurance are in place. A structured governance framework helps monitoring progress, promoting transparency, and maintaining accountability. Clear modeling guidelines, encapsulating the MBSE language, methods, tools, and personnel roles, should be documented in accessible formats, such as a model management plan or a collaborative wiki. Additionally, defining the scope and responsibilities of systems engineering within the organization fosters clarity and alignment across teams. Another important aspect is to establish coordination mechanisms at both technical and organizational levels to facilitate communication regarding domain, tools, and digital strategies. Organizations should remain committed to their vision, be resilient, learn from both successes and setbacks and continuously adjust the course to deliver incremental, demonstrable results. A culture of open communication and support can help guide their teams through the complexity of MBSE adoption [7][25][23][4][37][41].

Methodology, Language and Tools

- **C9: Choosing and Integrating Modeling Methodology and Tools**
 Selecting the right modeling methodology and tools is a difficult challenge in the transition to MBSE. The methodology serves as the guide for implementation, defining rules, guidelines, and processes that will be followed. Setting it up, documenting it, and creating supporting materials like training guides can be a resource intensive task. Customizing the method to fit the organization’s specific scope and purpose can further complicate this task. Additional extensions or adaptations to the methodology down the line can be challenging to implement [8][37][42].
 Equally important is the careful selection of the modeling tool. No single tool can satisfy all needs across the entire product life cycle, so it’s crucial to choose a tool that can integrate well with the company’s existing tool landscape. This integration is vital because different tasks will still require specialized tools, necessitating harmonized interfaces for effective data exchange. Tool incompatibility, lack of interoperability, and communication issues between different tools can significantly hinder MBSE adoption [8][3][15][2][20][38][37][42]. Nevertheless, focusing too heavily on tools rather than on the methodology can lead to misaligned efforts [20].
- **BP13: Capable IT Infrastructure**
 A robust and scalable IT infrastructure is fundamental to supporting MBSE adoption. The infrastructure should provide sufficient computing power, network performance, storage capacity, and access controls to handle the complexities of model data throughout the system’s life cycle. Failure to ensure an adequate IT setup can result in slowdowns, system bottlenecks, or even interruptions in model management. Proper infrastructure ensures that modeling tools can operate efficiently, preventing delays in deliveries and enabling smoother collaboration across the organization [6][32][25][15].
- **BP14: Tool Access**
 Providing widespread access to MBSE tools is important. Failure to do so can create divisions within the engineering team, jeopardizing the adoption of MBSE. Not every engineer will need the same level of access, but ensuring that those who need the tools, whether for model production or consumption, have appropriate licenses and access is essential. The cost of tool acquisition and licensing can be significant, so careful planning must account for both the needs of the organization and cost-effective solutions. Thoughtful distribution of licenses, aligned with roles, can lower costs and enhance collaboration [3][15][26][37].
- **BP15: Tool Selection and Integration**
 Ideally, an MBSE adoption effort considers the methodology and modeling language before selecting and integrating modeling tools. Many organizations make the mistake of focusing on tool acquisition too early, which can limit the benefits of MBSE if the tools do not fully align with the project’s needs. First, the capabilities the organization would like to develop by using MBSE should be identified, in order to decide on the tools that will help it fulfill

its goals. Then, proper tool integration with the existing tool landscape is crucial to ensure communication and data exchange between different tools across various engineering domains. Rushing into tool selection without understanding the organization’s modeling needs can lead to inefficiencies, limiting the potential impact of MBSE [3][28][34][43][15][27].

2.3 Level 3: Pilot Projects

Management

- **P4: Building on Shaky Foundation**

Relying on the models from pilot projects as a foundation for further development can be a pitfall. There is a high risk in building on a shaky foundation to avoid the cost of establishing a stronger, more reliable base. It’s crucial to recognize that pilot models are often preliminary and may require significant refinement. Stakeholders should be cautious about the temptation to extend these initial models without addressing underlying issues, as this can perpetuate foundational weaknesses and impact the overall effectiveness of the MBSE approach [28].

- **P5: Lack of Tool Support**

Starting modeling efforts without a local tool support team can be a significant pitfall. Engineers need a reliable environment to work effectively. Otherwise, issues with tools and infrastructure can hinder progress and lead to frustration. Without proper setup and support, users may struggle with tooling difficulties, which can derail their objectives and result in misplaced blame on the MBSE adoption effort, rather than addressing the root causes of the problems [4].

- **BP16: Facilitate Communication**

An essential best practice for management during MBSE adoption is ensuring effective communication across all stakeholders. A clear communication plan should specify who communicates what, how, and when, with follow-up protocols to ensure alignment and accountability. Regular updates on the transition’s timeline, strategy, and objectives, shared through tools such as webinars, emails, and meetings, foster engagement and ensure the plan remains realistic. Open and frequent communication of risks, protocols, and progress across departments is vital, with digital artifacts serving as effective tools for sharing information. Close coordination between the MBSE development team and systems engineers is particularly critical early on to align expectations, manage scope, and address trade-offs between implementation feasibility and immediate system engineering needs. While MBSE provides a single source of truth to streamline communication, the full potential of this benefit can only be achieved when management actively promotes and facilitates these practices, ensuring transparency, collaboration, and shared understanding throughout the organization [14][9][34][25][15][37].

- **BP17: Avoid the Sunk Cost Fallacy in Pilot Projects**

Another best practice in MBSE adoption is recognizing that pilot projects are primarily for learning and experimentation, not for creating final models.

Organizations should approach pilot efforts with the mindset that the value lies in the lessons learned, the insights gained, and the experience of using system modeling tools, not in the models themselves. If the pilot toolset or models prove unsuitable for long-term goals, be willing to change direction or tools. By treating pilot models as prototypes and focusing on gaining expertise, organizations can avoid the fallacy of building on an unstable foundation simply to preserve prior investments [28][29]. Additionally, when using prototypes, scaling must be carefully considered. Prototypes that cover too small a scope may not reveal critical issues that arise at larger scales, leading to false assumptions about the feasibility of MBSE implementations. Prototyping is valuable, but ensuring the prototype reflects the appropriate scope is essential for identifying potential challenges [14]. Having this in mind allows for the flexibility to ensure that future MBSE efforts are built on validated, reliable solutions, rather than prematurely building on top of pilot outcomes.

Methodology, Language and Tools

– C10: Lack of Standardization in Modeling Language Usage

SysML is often seen as the de facto standard for MBSE, but its complexity and vast range of possibilities can be overwhelming, especially for new users. Regardless of what modeling language is chosen, but especially when it is similar in complexity to SysML, it is important to realize that not all features need to be utilized, it is crucial for organizations to establish a company-wide standard for how the modeling language will be used. By restricting the use of certain features and keeping models simple, organizations can make MBSE more accessible to stakeholders and ensure that models remain clear and functional. Without those standards, the risk increases that models will vary significantly in style and structure, making it challenging for colleagues or stakeholders to understand and work with them effectively [14][20].

– BP18: Customize and Integrate Tools

Another important step in MBSE adoption is customizing and integrating the chosen modeling tool into the organization's existing toolchain. This process typically involves extending / limiting the tool's language capabilities, implementing validation rules, and developing automated scripts to align the tool with both the modeling methodology and organizational needs. Customization efforts could for example work on optimizing the tool by making frequently used elements easily accessible while removing unused ones. The main challenge often arises in integrating the MBSE tool with other essential engineering tools, e.g. those used for testing and simulation. Ensuring interoperability through open interfaces is vital, as it facilitates seamless import and export processes across different design phases and prevents reliance on proprietary tools, which can cause issues down the road. In this context, it can be very helpful to have technically knowledgeable support staff assisting engineers. These well-defined interfaces and consistent modeling standards

across teams will help tremendously for successful integration. By integrating the MBSE tool effectively, organizations can simplify workflows, reduce the need for redundant tools, and improve communication and collaboration across teams [7][3][43][15].

Modeling

– C11: Lack of Clear Modeling Purpose

As organizations progress to the stage of pilot projects and begin actual modeling efforts, one key challenge is defining the specific purposes of each model. While high-level MBSE goals are clear, many struggle to ensure that individual models are tailored to answer well-defined questions or meet specific project needs. Without this clarity, there is a risk of overmodeling or creating models for the sake of modeling, which can lead to inefficiencies and models that are not as effective or communicative as they could be [28].

Additionally, models should be designed with the users in mind. Many people across various disciplines will interact with the models, and not all have the same level of knowledge or expertise. Querying the model often requires additional training. Overcomplicating models or cramming too much into one can further impede navigation and understanding, leading to overlap with other models and resulting in inconsistency and inefficiency. Therefore, it's important to keep models simple and purposeful, ensuring they are easy to navigate and able to accomplish their primary objectives [8][29].

– C12: Off-Cycle vs. On-Cycle

Deciding on the beginning modeling effort whether to introduce MBSE during an actual project with real clients and deliverables (on-cycle) or to test it in a controlled, off-cycle sandbox environment can be challenging. In an on-cycle adoption, the pressure is high, as there are real-world consequences, timelines, and client expectations. This can lead to rushed implementation and difficulty addressing unexpected challenges. Conversely, off-cycle adoption provides the team with space to experiment and refine their MBSE approach without the pressure of a live project. However, the gap between sandbox experimentation and applying MBSE in real-world projects can create difficulties in translating theoretical knowledge into practical execution [8][15].

This transition problem is often described by the "blank page syndrome", where individuals struggle to begin creating meaningful models for real systems after learning MBSE theory and practicing on generic examples. Unlike working on predefined examples, applying MBSE to the specific needs of the target system can feel overwhelming [2][42].

– P6: Aimless modelling

A key pitfall when modeling is the failure to define a clear purpose and scope for each model. Without a specific goal, modeling can become aimless, leading to overcomplicated models that do not effectively answer stakeholder questions. The focus should be on system engineering rather than modeling. A model should be driven by its ability to address engineering questions and

needs. If a model does not satisfy the requirements of stakeholders or provide the necessary engineering insights, it is incomplete. This lack of focus can lead to delivering models that seem finished, but fail to provide the required engineering answers. Effective modeling requires a clear understanding of competency questions and the scope of the model to ensure that it serves its intended purpose [43][15][21][4][44].

– **P7: Overmodeling**

Overmodeling is a typical pitfall during the beginning modeling effort of MBSE. The extensive capabilities of the modeling languages (e.g. SysML) lead to excessively detailed models. This can result in models that are cumbersome and difficult to manage, as each additional model element requires significant follow-up work, such as updates to definitions, diagrams, and simulations. Overmodeling not only increases the complexity of the model but also diminishes its usefulness, as the effort to maintain and update the model often outweighs its benefits. Effective modeling should prioritize critical system components and avoid mixing different engineering levels within the same model, as this can lead to significant refactoring and inefficiencies [43][15][4][44].

– **P8: Poor Model Architecture**

Another critical pitfall in MBSE adoption is poor model architecture, which can manifest as large, monolithic models with excessive usage levels and circular references between projects. Sometimes multiple engineering levels are combined within a single model under the illusion of simplicity. For example, merging the architectural design of a system with that of its subsystems within the same model. This can lead to significant complications, such as cumbersome refactoring and integration difficulties. Effective model architecture requires clear boundaries and a well-structured organization to maintain control and comprehensibility throughout the development process. Without these structures, issues such as duplicate elements, broken traceability and others can arise. Ensuring a well-organized model architecture with defined package structures and clear separation of concerns is essential to avoid this pitfall and support a successful MBSE implementation [32][15][21][30][44].

– **P9: Lack of Modeling Standards**

Another pitfall is the absence of modeling standards. Without standardized rules for modeling practices, there is a risk of developing highly sophisticated and unique models that are not easily understood or integrated across the organization. Often, a small group of modelers may create detailed models using complex or non-standard elements, leading to "Ivory Tower" scenarios where these models are comprehensible only to their creators. Such models, while technically accurate, can become isolated from broader development processes, diminishing their utility and impact. This lack of standardization makes collaboration and integration challenging. Implementing clear, company-wide modeling standards is crucial to ensure models are understandable, consistent, and valuable across the organization [32][43].

– **BP19: Clear Modeling Purpose**

When embarking on any modeling initiative, it is essential to clearly define the model's purpose. These purposes should be articulated as specific questions that the model is intended to answer. This way the model is clearly finished when all relevant questions can be answered, which ensures that models do not get overmodelled and unnecessarily complex, helping to prevent wasted effort, frustration, and low recognition of the model's benefits. If models are created without clear goals tied to supporting key engineering activities, they risk delivering little value and generating low stakeholder buy-in. By aligning each model with specific, measurable outcomes and reducing unnecessary maintenance efforts, organizations can ensure that MBSE drives meaningful results and supports business objectives effectively. Clear modeling objectives provide the necessary focus to produce knowledge, streamline engineering tasks, and deliver tangible benefits, rather than creating models for modeling's sake [14][7][28][29][4][11].

– **BP20: Plan and Build a Good Model Architecture**

A best practice in early modeling efforts for the MBSE adoption is to carefully plan the model architecture to maintain clarity and manage complexity. Large, overly complex diagrams can hinder understanding and productivity, while the true strength of MBSE lies in the ability to query models and generate specific views / diagrams or reports as needed. Views / diagrams, just as the model itself, should be purpose-driven, focusing on answering specific questions with only the necessary information included. To manage complexity, diagrams should be structured hierarchically, breaking down large systems into smaller, more digestible diagrams, capturing key concepts at each level. However, it has to be acknowledged that model architecture and modeling are iterative processes. Early in the model development life cycle, decisions around both the scope (breadth) and level of detail (depth) should be explored simultaneously, ensuring the architecture can support future growth and prevent technical debt from building up. Researching and testing different levels of depth and breadth helps uncover architecture drivers, such as differences in system structure or direct interfaces between components deep within the hierarchy, and allows for continuous refinement based on feedback. This iterative approach ensures flexibility as the model grows, allowing the architecture to evolve through input from stakeholders and engineers. The goal is not to perfect the model or architecture from the outset, but to iteratively improve it based on real-world usage, gradually expanding its value and relevance for the entire organization. A well-planned architectural vision, especially using reference architectures, ensures a logical structure that aids communication, stakeholder engagement and scalability, ultimately making the model more effective as it evolves [28][29][23][41][5].

– **BP21: Rigor, Formalism and Standardization**

Establishing formal guidelines and standardization in modeling is critical, especially in the early stages of MBSE adoption. Modeling languages such as SysML provide incredible flexibility, but without formalized guidelines, the resulting models can vary widely between modelers, which can become overwhelming for teams with limited model / modeling experience, reducing

their effectiveness and leading to confusion. To ensure consistency and interoperability across teams, formal modeling guidelines, standardized rules, and simplified language (e.g. SysML) constructs should be adopted early. These constraints help streamline the modeling process, improve clarity, and make it easier for all stakeholders to understand and work with the models. As the number of users grows, the need for rigor increases, and having standardized practices in place ensures scalability and reduces complexity. Creating enterprise-wide modeling standards promotes coherence and alignment across projects, making the transition to MBSE smoother and more efficient [14][17][15][4][7][28][32][25][2][24][23][26].

– **BP22: Start MBSE with New Projects**

Beginning MBSE adoption with a new project is often a more effective approach than converting existing document-based projects. New projects eliminate the risk of importing outdated workflows, errors, or shortcuts that can undermine the learning and application of MBSE. By starting from scratch, teams focus on learning the methodology without relying on existing artifacts that may compromise the MBSE process. Moreover, existing projects often have fixed budgets and deadlines that do not account for the additional time and resources needed for MBSE training, making it harder to succeed under those constraints [3][34]. However, not every company has a new project suitable for the beginning of this transition. In those cases, it can be a best practice to start with converting well-documented, reusable artifacts from previous projects. These detailed artifacts allow developers to focus on learning the MBSE methodology rather than on content creation. Furthermore the existing artifacts can be used for verification and validation of the new models. As long as the risks of this approach are understood and measures taken to avoid translating errors of past projects into MBSE, this approach can be used and adds most value when the artifacts are likely to be reused in future MBSE efforts, ensuring the effort contributes beyond just learning purposes [3].

– **BP23: Validation and Verification of Models**

Ensuring the accuracy and quality of models from the start is critical. To maintain model consistency and completeness, it is essential to implement both manual and automated validation processes. Manual validation can involve regular model reviews that include not just the model creators but also domain experts to ensure all relevant stakeholders are engaged. Automated validation tools can further help by applying rules to check for model consistency and completeness, reducing errors early in development. Properly validated models give stakeholders confidence in their predictive capabilities, supporting early virtual validation of system performance and behavior. Additionally, involving subsystem stakeholders in co-engineering activities ensures that transitions between system levels are accurate, feasible, and align with the perspectives of all engineering teams. This ongoing validation throughout the system lifecycle prevents issues later on and solidifies the model's role as a reliable reference across the organization [7][32][4].

– **BP24: Real Value Projects**

Another often mentioned best practice for MBSE adoption is to start with real projects that bring tangible value to the organization, rather than mock-up or sandbox projects. Working on real projects with actual deadlines and deliverables enhances motivation, as engineers see their efforts contributing directly to the organization’s goals. In a real-world setting, employees are required to fully engage with MBSE, ensuring they learn and apply it in a meaningful way. If the project is purely for training, there’s less urgency, leaving room for incomplete learning and procrastination. Real projects, aligned with the organization’s domain, help highlight MBSE’s practical benefits and demonstrate its value, motivating stakeholders to commit to the transition. This is further amplified when the focus lies on high-impact use cases, for example change impact analysis. These tasks that are time-consuming and error-prone when done with traditional methods can shift people from skepticism, when the benefits of MBSE are demonstrated with them. Additionally, using MBSE to generate real deliverables such as documents, reports etc. further strengthens adoption by showing how MBSE can streamline daily activities and improve communication among project stakeholders. Providing real-world success examples can add to justifying the initial investment and help gain broader acceptance within the organization [3][28][29][25][15][42].

2.4 Level 4: Scaling MBSE adoption

Management

– C13: Increased Rigor and Model Management

Models are not static, they require continuous management, updates, and data integration to remain relevant and useful throughout the product life cycle. Without verification, validation, configuration control, and quality checks, the value of models can quickly diminish. To ensure models remain trusted engineering artifacts, organizations must commit to rigorous planning and processes, treating the MBSE environment as a key component of the digital engineering ecosystem [32].

– C14: Transitioning to the Model as the Main Artifact

Shifting from documents to the system model as the primary artifact can be difficult for stakeholders not yet comfortable with the model-based approach. Decisions must be made on when to generate documents versus conducting reviews and meetings directly within the model using the modeling tool. Reviews conducted directly from the models can have limited success, especially with external experts who are not proficient with the modeling tools. Tailoring model views to specific domains is necessary to make the information digestible for various stakeholders. Until the automatic generation of gate products from models is fully mature, it is important to allocate adequate schedule time and margin for document generation, as technical issues may arise that need to be addressed before delivery [14][2][10][1].

– **P10: Failing to enforce MBSE**

When MBSE is starting to become a central part of development another pitfall can emerge. When MBSE is encouraged but not enforced, it can happen that both approaches are used simultaneously, leading to inconsistent practices within a project. Some team members may embrace modeling, while others continue working with traditional document-based methods. This disjointed approach can cause confusion and inefficiency, particularly when deadlines approach. Under pressure, people often revert to familiar ways of working, abandoning the MBSE transition. This creates a "Model Island" where the models exist in isolation, disconnected from the rest of the development process. For MBSE to succeed, modeling must be fully integrated and mandatory, replacing traditional activities and ensuring that all stakeholders are aligned with the model-based approach. If left optional, modeling efforts are often the first to be discarded under pressure, undermining the transition to MBSE and reducing its potential benefits [43]

– **P11: Poor Management and Use of Reusable Model Libraries**

The pitfall of poor management and enforcement of reuse libraries occurs when libraries of reusable models are not properly maintained or consistently enforced. Without clear guidelines, teams may fail to use existing models effectively, leading to duplication of effort, inconsistencies, and wasted time. The effective management of reuse libraries ensures that models are accessible, standardized, and used across projects [32].

– **BP25: Make Models the Centerpiece Artifact**

The final best practice at this stage is to commit to making the models the centerpiece artifact for referencing architecture, converting requirements into designs, and tracing verification and validation tasks throughout the design process. By prioritizing models, organizations ensure that changes begin with the model itself, reinforcing its role as the primary design reference. It is essential to allocate continuous resources for updating and sustaining these models, employing them as the foundation for design reviews and verifying requirements. With adequate training, stakeholders can conduct design reviews directly from the modeling tool, allowing them to witness firsthand how key elements of MBSE, such as reuse, modularity and encapsulation, enhance consistency, traceability and overall design quality. Regular model reviews should actively involve model contributors and domain experts, utilizing model files rather than static images to facilitate more effective discussions. While models serve as the main artifact, it can be a good practice to restrict access to certain parts of the model to prevent overwhelming users with excessive views and options that are only relevant for particular experts. Positioning models at the heart of the engineering workflow may require changes to organizational processes, but stepwise replacement of traditional activities and making sure that all stakeholder are aligned with the model-based approach is necessary for MBSE to succeed [6][5][15][24][26][39].

Modeling

- **C15: Balancing Model Complexity and Flexibility**

The challenge lies in finding a balance between creating models that address immediate needs without overcomplicating them, while also ensuring they are flexible enough to accommodate future applications and growth. Overly simplistic models may require large revisions as project requirements expand, whereas overly complex models can become inefficient and difficult to maintain. Building models with an eye toward future adaptability helps manage technical debt and ensures their longevity within the MBSE ecosystem [28][29].

- **C16: Reusability and Model Libraries**

When starting the modeling effort, there is no established library of reusable system models. Everything must be built from scratch. This process is time-consuming, especially for inexperienced modelers who may need training or rely on the limited availability of experienced modelers. Reusability isn't simply copying and pasting models from one context to another, as this approach compromises the "single source of truth" once either the source or target model is modified. Establishing modularity and reusability requires careful planning to ensure consistency and efficiency across the system models [8][35][42].

- **BP26: Leverage the Network Effect**

An important best practice at this stage is to capitalize on the network effect by making models relevant to a wide range of stakeholders. As more stakeholders engage with the model, its value increases through broader adoption and reuse as well as a broader audience of users fueling its continuing maintenance and evolution. Integrating and using models across collaborating systems allows for better insights into interdependencies at the enterprise level, which can improve decision-making. By expanding the scope of the model to address the needs of various stakeholders and system life cycle phases as well as making it a recognized reference, organizations can drive greater involvement and amplify the benefits of MBSE. This network effect accelerates the adoption of MBSE, as the initial investment in model creation is offset by the model's growing utility and value across the organization. The vision is to create a system representation that allows various stakeholders to extract artifacts for their own specific use [28][3][29][4][42][6].

- **BP27: Focus on the Underlying Data, Not Just the Diagrams**

While the diagrams are often the most visible and tangible products of the MBSE approach, the real power and value lie in the underlying data that supports those diagrams. The true potential of MBSE comes from how it captures, integrates, and manages a multi-layered network of elements, attributes, and relationships in electronic format. This data allows the system to be queried, analyzed, and manipulated in ways that traditional methods cannot achieve, enabling the creation of customized views that trace relationships between components, requirements, or functions. It is crucial to build models with a focus on supporting data input, management and exchange, ensuring that the data is easily accessible and usable. The more data a model integrates, the more valuable it becomes for representing, simulating,

and validating different aspects of the system. This ensures that models are not just static visual representations but dynamic tools that enable deeper insights and decision-making across the system’s lifecycle [28][29][15].

– **BP28: Maintain and Update Models**

Once MBSE has been adopted beyond pilot projects, maintaining and keeping models up to date becomes a critical best practice to ensure long-term success. Models must evolve together with the system and the organization’s understanding of it. A model that is not actively maintained will quickly lose its relevance and usefulness, leading to a vicious cycle where outdated models are not used, and therefore, don’t receive the resources needed to be kept current. To break this cycle, models should be treated as living artifacts that provide continuous value to stakeholders. The key to ensuring that models remain useful is to make them the main source for answering system-related questions, and to provide automation where possible. Automating data updates and exchanges can significantly reduce the manual effort needed to keep models accurate, especially when drawing from existing databases or external data sources. By integrating MBSE models with these external sources and automating data refreshes, the risk of inconsistencies is minimized, and the labor required to maintain the models is reduced. Where manual updates are necessary, creating user-friendly interfaces that allow domain experts (not just modeling experts) to input data ensures that the burden of model maintenance doesn’t fall solely on a small team of modelers. This creates a virtuous cycle: the more models are used, the more they are maintained, which in turn increases their value, relevance, and use. By ensuring models stay current and relevant, they can continue to grow in value and serve as a reliable, central resource for the organization’s decision-making processes. Models should be viewed and treated as key components of the digital engineering ecosystem, which requires similar rigor and management to vital software components that are responsible for providing and maintaining engineering data across the entire system life cycle [28][29][32][25].

– **BP29: Build Flexibility into Models for Future Growth**

As MBSE scales within an organization, it is critical to build flexibility into system models to accommodate future growth and new applications. Early investments in flexible model architectures can significantly reduce the accumulation of technical debt, ensuring that models remain adaptable and sustainable over time. This flexibility enables models to evolve alongside system requirements, preventing the need for major rework when expanding the model’s scope or functionality. Experienced model architects should focus on balancing immediate needs with long-term adaptability, avoiding overly rigid designs that limit future use cases. By incorporating this flexibility up front, organizations can ensure that their MBSE approach remains responsive to changing demands, improving model usability, maintainability, and scalability over time [28][29][15][31].

– **BP30: Develop Model Libraries and Promote Modularity**

A key best practice when scaling MBSE adoption is to start developing and utilizing libraries of reusable model elements. As organizations gain experi-

ence through pilot projects, the creation of libraries for interfaces, components, and other reusable system elements becomes essential for accelerating future projects. Establishing modular and reusable libraries like interface-, component-, or unit-libraries, enables teams to avoid starting from scratch for each project, streamlining model development and fostering consistency across efforts. Modular Open Systems Architecture (MOSA) principles can be employed to design major system interfaces that comply with widely supported standards, facilitating the reuse of requirements, designs, and test artifacts across multiple projects. These steps not only help with model partitioning and the reuse of elements, but also support and encourage broader MBSE adoption by providing ready to use, reference model elements that allow new projects to begin with a solid foundation. Over time, this practice enables teams to build models more efficiently, ensures consistency in system development, and reduces costs associated with recreating common elements. By making reusable models and modularity a cornerstone of the MBSE process, organizations can significantly accelerate project timelines and drive the successful scaling of MBSE across the enterprise [7][32][15][2][24][42][31].

– **BP31: Use of Documents in MBSE**

Another best practice in the adoption of MBSE at this stage is to recognize that the need for readable documents alongside the transition to model-centric practices remains. It is important to acknowledge that not all stakeholders may engage with models directly from the beginning. Some disciplines might not be as involved in modeling or are slow in adopting new concepts of operation, but are reliant on the results. Therefore, there should be mechanisms in place to extract traditional systems engineering artifacts from models to accommodate those who are not accustomed to working directly with models. This visualization and conversion of modeled content into document- and presentation-reports are necessary to stay communicative to all teams and customers. Automated methods for document generation and integration from model-driven development play a critical role in this process, ensuring that design updates are consistently reflected in the generated documents. This dual approach allows organizations to leverage the advantages of MBSE while still meeting the traditional needs of stakeholders who may be less agile in adopting new paradigms. As companies transition to MBSE, maintaining the capability to produce communicative reports and documentation will facilitate smoother interactions with different domains, suppliers and partners that rely on traditional practices, ultimately leading to a less intrusive introduction of MBSE [14][15][2][37][12][39].

References

1. Akundi, A., Ankobiah, W.: Mapping industry workforce needs to academic curricula – a workforce development effort in model-based systems engineering. *Systems Engineering* **27**(4), 685–698 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21745>
2. Alvarez, J.L., de Koning, H.P., Fischer, D., Wallum, M., Metselaar, H., Kretzenbacher, M.: Best practices for model based systems engineering in esa projects.

- In: 2018 AIAA SPACE and Astronautics Forum and Exposition (2018). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2018-5327>
3. Amorim, T., Vogelsang, A., Pudlitz, F., Gersing, P., Philipps, J.: Strategies and best practices for model-based systems engineering adoption in embedded systems industry. In: 2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Practice (ICSE-SEIP). pp. 203–212 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-SEIP.2019.00030>
 4. Bonnet, S., Voirin, J.L., Normand, V., Exertier, D.: Implementing the mbse cultural change: Organization, coaching and lessons learned. INCOSE International Symposium **25**(1), 508–523 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2015.00078.x>
 5. Call, D.R., Herber, D.R.: Applicability of the diffusion of innovation theory to accelerate model-based systems engineering adoption. *Systems Engineering* **25**(6), 574–583 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21638>
 6. Carroll, E.R., Malins, R.J.: Systematic literature review: How is model-based systems engineering justified? (3 2016). <https://doi.org/10.2172/1561164>
 7. Chami, M., Aleksandraviciene, A., Morkevicius, A., Bruel, J.M.: Towards solving mbse adoption challenges: The d3 mbse adoption toolbox. INCOSE International Symposium **28**(1), 1463–1477 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2018.00561.x>
 8. Chami, M., Bruel, J.M.: A survey on mbse adoption challenges. In: INCOSE EMEA Sector Systems Engineering Conference (INCOSE EMEASEC 2018). pp. 1–16. Berlin, Germany (November 2018)
 9. Dawson, S., Batchelor, A.: Empowering engineers in a digital engineering transition: Applying organizational psychology and systems thinking approaches to define the problem and to develop recommended actions. INCOSE International Symposium **32**(1), 594–607 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/iis2.12951>
 10. Dubos, G., Schreiner, S., Wagner, D.A., Jones, G., Kerzhner, A.A., Kaderka, J.: Architecture modeling on the europa project. In: AIAA SPACE 2016 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2016-5310>
 11. Faudou, R., Bruel, J.M.: An industrial feedback on model-based requirements engineering in systems engineering context. In: 2016 IEEE 24th International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW). pp. 190–199 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/REW.2016.042>
 12. Ferguson, R., Marshall, J., Guzman, M.: Adapting progressive mbse development to document based contracts. In: 2020 IEEE Aerospace Conference. pp. 1–11 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/AERO47225.2020.9172671>
 13. Gustavsson, H., Enoiu, E.P., Carlson, J.: Model-based system engineering adoption in the vehicular systems domain. In: 2022 17th Conference on Computer Science and Intelligence Systems (FedCSIS). pp. 907–911 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.15439/2022F47>
 14. Hallqvist, J., Larsson, J.: Introducing mbse by using systems engineering principles. INCOSE International Symposium **26**(1), 512–525 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2016.00175.x>
 15. Henderson, K., McDermott, T., Salado, A.: Mbse adoption experiences in organizations: Lessons learned. *Systems Engineering* **27**(1), 214–239 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21717>
 16. Henderson, K., McDermott, T., Van Aken, E., Salado, A.: Towards developing metrics to evaluate digital engineering. *Systems Engineering* **26**(1), 3–31 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21640>

17. Henderson, K., Salado, A.: The effects of organizational structure on mbse adoption in industry: Insights from practitioners. *Engineering Management Journal* **36**(1), 117–143 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10429247.2023.2210494>
18. Holladay, J.B., Knizhnik, J., Weiland, K.J., Stein, A., Sanders, T., Schwindt, P.: Mbse infusion and modernization initiative (miami): “hot” benefits for real nasa applications. In: 2019 IEEE Aerospace Conference. pp. 1–14 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/AERO.2019.8741795>
19. Huldt, T., Stenius, I.: State-of-practice survey of model-based systems engineering. *Systems Engineering* **22**(2), 134–145 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21466>
20. Khandoker, A., Sint, S., Gessl, G., Zeman, K., Jungreitmayr, F., Wahl, H., Wenigwieser, A., Kretschmer, R.: Towards a logical framework for ideal mbse tool selection based on discipline specific requirements. *Journal of Systems and Software* **189**, 111306 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2022.111306>
21. Lerat, J.P.: 5.5.2 three reasons why document-based se (usually) works better than (most of) mbse. *INCOSE International Symposium* **20**(1), 723–738 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2010.tb01100.x>
22. Li, T., Pollettini Marcos, L., Huang, W., Kenley, C.R., Douglas, K.A., Madsen, E.A., Fentiman, A.W.: Learning mbse online: A tale of two professional cohorts. *Systems* **11**(5) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/systems11050224>
23. Mancin, E.: How model based systems engineering streamlines the development of complex systems. In: *INCOSE Italia Conference on Systems Engineering* (2014), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:14621075>
24. McDermott, T., Henderson, K., Van Aken, E., Salado, A., Bradley, J.: Measuring the roi of digital engineering: It’s a journey, not a number. *AIRC Perspectives* pp. 1–8 (2022), <https://acqirc.org/airc-perspectives/measuring-the-roi-of-digital-engineering-its-a-journey-not-a-number/>
25. McDermott, T., Henderson, K., Van Aken, E., Salado, A.: Framework for and progress of adoption of digital and model-based systems engineering into engineering enterprises. In: *The Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Systems Engineering Research*. pp. 69–82. Springer Nature Switzerland (2024)
26. Mitchell, S.W.: Transitioning the swfts program combat system product family from traditional document-centric to model-based systems engineering. *Systems Engineering* **17**(3), 313–329 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sys.21271>
27. Nanfuka, J.G., Oosthuizen, R.: Mbse-lite: A framework for adopting model-based systems engineering in small and medium-sized enterprises in south africa. *Business, Management and Economics Engineering* **21**, 218–236 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3846/bmee.2023.19170>
28. Noguchi, R.A.: Recommended best practices based on mbse pilot projects. *INCOSE International Symposium* **29**(1), 753–770 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2019.00633.x>
29. Noguchi, R.A., Minnichelli, R.J., Wheaton, M.J.: Architecting success in model based systems engineering pilot projects. In: 2019 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics (SMC). pp. 755–760 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMC.2019.8914417>
30. Orosz, M., Duffy, B., Charlton, C., Saunders, H., Thomas, E.: Unique challenges in mission engineering and technology integration. In: *Systems Engineering for the Digital Age*. pp. 665–681. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781394203314.ch31>

31. Papke, B., Hause, M., Hetherington, D.: Fuse agility as a foundation for sound mbse lifecycle management. *INSIGHT* **26**(2), 34–38 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/inst.12443>
32. Papke, B., Hause, M., Hetherington, D., McGervey, S., Rodriguez, S.: Mbse model management pain points – wait, this looks familiar! *INCOSE International Symposium* **33**(1), 273–289 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/iis2.13021>
33. Papke, B.L., Wang, G., Kratzke, R., Schreiber, C.: Implementing mbse – an enterprise approach to an enterprise problem. *INCOSE International Symposium* **30**(1), 1550–1567 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2020.00803.x>
34. Ploeg, C., Lai, K., Olechowski, A.: Prioritization of best practices in the implementation of model-based systems engineering. *INCOSE International Symposium* **32**(1), 961–975 (2022)
35. Pratt, M., Dabkowski, M.: Analyzing the integration of mbse approaches within the aerospace industry according to utaut. *Industrial and Systems Engineering Review* **10**(2), 127–134 (Dec 2022). <https://doi.org/10.37266/ISER.2022v10i2.pp127-134>
36. Schumacher, T., Ammersdörfer, T., Inkermann, D.: Development and application of simulation games to introduce model-based systems engineering. In: *Towards a new future in engineering education, new scenarios that european alliances of tech universities open up*. p. 702–709. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Sep 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5821/conference-9788412322262.1420>
37. Sindiy, O., Mozafari, T., Budney, C.: Application of model-based systems engineering for the development of the asteroid redirect robotic mission. In: *AIAA SPACE 2016* (2016). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2016-5312>
38. Suryadevara, J., Tiwari, S.: Adopting mbse in construction equipment industry: An experience report. In: *2018 25th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference (APSEC)*. pp. 512–521 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/APSEC.2018.00066>
39. Vasenev, A., Suermondt, W.T., Behl, A., Lukkien, J.: Step-wise mbse introduction into a company: An interface-centric case study. In: *2023 18th Annual System of Systems Engineering Conference (SoSe)*. pp. 1–6 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SoSE59841.2023.10178600>
40. Vogelsang, A., Amorim, T., Pudlitz, F., Gersing, P., Philipps, J.: Should i stay or should i go? on forces that drive and prevent mbse adoption in the embedded systems industry (2017), <https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.00266>
41. Wang, G.: Implementing a model-based, digital engineering enterprise for a defense systems integrator – an ongoing journey. *INCOSE International Symposium* **30**(1), 783–798 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.2020.00755.x>
42. Wang, L., Izygon, M., Okon, S., Wagner, H., Garner, L.: Effort to accelerate mbse adoption and usage at jsc. In: *AIAA SPACE 2016* (2016). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2016-5542>
43. Weilkiens, T.: Adoption of mbse in an organization. In: *Handbook of Model-Based Systems Engineering*. pp. 1–19. Springer International Publishing (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27486-3_18-1
44. Zhu, H., McDermott, A.: Optimal architecting strategy for partially developed products: Challenges and solutions. In: *2023 IEEE International Systems Conference*. pp. 1–6 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SysCon53073.2023.10131213>